

Table 1: The names of the sirās.

The 18 sirās of the 8x8 vāstu.

According to PI 8.10-12

According to Anantaśambhu, in his
commentary to the Siddhāntasārāvalī, 150
(taken from SŚ part 3 587)

east-west	north-south	east-west	north-south
Śriyā	Dhanyā	Lakṣmī	Dhanyā
Yaśovatī	Dhanā	Yaśovatī	Prāṇā
Kāntā	Viśālā	Kāntā	Viśālā
Supriyā	Sthirā	Svapriyā	Sthirā
Vimalā	Bhadrā	Vimalā	Bhadrā
Śivā	Gadā	Śivā	Jayā
Suśobhā	Niśā	Subhagā	Niśā
Bhā	Virajā	Sumatī	Virajā
Nunī	Vibhavā	Sārā	Vibhavā

The 20 sirās of the 9x9 vāstu.

According to PI 9.3-6

According to Utpala in his commentary
on BS 52.65

east-west	north-south	east-west	north-south
Śāntā	Hiranyā	Śāntā	Hiranyā
Yaśovatī	Suprabhā	Yaśovatī	Suvratā
Kāntā	Lakṣmī	Kāntā	Lakṣmī
Viśālā	Vibhūti	Viśālā	Vibhūti
Prāṇavāhiṇī	Vimalā	Prāṇavāhiṇī	Vimalā
Satī	Śriyā	Satī	Priyā
Sumatī	Jayā	Sumanā	Jayā
Nandā	Jvalā	Nandā	Kālā
Subhadrā	Viśokā	Subhadrā	Viśokā
Manoramā	Śubhā	Surathā	Indrā

Table 2: lists of marman names

BK vy 142-3	MY as quoted by Trilocana at SŚ vol. 4, p.49	PI 8.18-19
list of 12	list of 12	list of 13
vajra	sandhi	padma
lāṅgala	mahāmarman	vajra
śūla, etc.	ambuja	sandhi
maṇibandha, etc.	saṃpuṭa	pada
padma	hala	lāṅgala
svastika	svastika	saṃpuṭa
śuddha	mahāsvastika	triśūla
mahāmarman, etc.	vajra	maṇibandha
	śūla	trikaṭa
	maṇibandha	svastika
	trikaṭa	vaṃśa
	suviśuddhapada	raju
		nāḍī

Table 3: Śalyas as indicated by scratching

place scratched	śalya type	depth
head:		
PI 9.76	head	tatpramāṇataḥ
MY 4 x+14cd	bone	at ½ a man
KI 54.40ab	elephant śalya	at ½ a man
DM 80.68c-69b	bone	at ½ a man
face:		
PI 9.77	wood	2 hastas
MY 4 x+15	wood	2 hastas
KI 54.40	wood	2 hastas
DM 80.69c-70b	wood / hair of head	2 hastas
neck:		
PI 9.78	chain	3 hastas
MY 4 x+15	chain	3 hastas
	or cat skeleton	½ a man
KI 54.41	chain	3 hastas
	or animal	4 hastas
DM 80.71c-72b	chain	3 hastas
hand:		
PI 9.79-80	bed	32 aṅgulas
MY 4 x+19	bed post	1 hasta
KI 54.42	bed	knee deep
DM 80.75c-77b	bed post	knee deep
	or skull or something made of clay	hip deep
arm:		
KI 54.42	long bone	3 hastas
MY 4 x+18	human arm bone	hip depth
DM 80.74c-75b	bone	3 ½ hastas
left upper arm:		
PI 9.80-82	arm	arm depth
	or something made of clay	
right upper arm:		
PI 9.80-82	bowl	hip depth
	or something made of clay	
hip:		
PI 9.82-83	iron spike	2 hastas
MY 4 x+20	iron spike	2 hastas
KI 54.44	iron ring	2 hastas
DM 80.80c-81b	iron spike	2 hastas
	or hip	
thigh:		
PI 9.83-84	hard wood	1 ½ hastas
MYcomm 4 after x+21	hard wood	1 ½ hastas
KI 54.45	wood	12 aṅgulas

knee:		
MYcomm 4 after x+21	wood or barber's blade	1 hasta 1 hasta
PI 9.84-85	wood or barber's blade	1 hasta 1 hasta
KI 54.45	barber's equipment	1 hasta
DM 80.82c-83b	post or barber's equipment	knee deep 1 hasta
shin:		
DM 80.83c-84b	shin	11 añgulas
ankle:		
PI 9.85-86	horse hoof	18 añgulas
MYcomm 4 after x+21	horse hoof	3 parts less than a hasta
KI 54.46	horse hoof	12 añgulas
foot:		
MYcomm 4 after x+21	tusk	1 hasta
PI 9.86-87	tusk	1 tāla
KI 54.46	elephant bone	12 añgulas
DM 80.84c-85b	elephant śalya	12 añgulas
big toe:		
PI 9.87-88	chalk	16 añgulas
DM 80.85c-86b	chalk, brass or figured iron	?
KI 54.43	shield	3 hastas
MYcomm 4 after x+21	brass	?
middle toe:		
MYcomm 4 after x+21	brass	?
DM 80.86c-87b	horse hoof	13 ½ añgulas
little toe:		
PI 9.88-89	brass	8 añgulas
MYcomm 4 after x+21	brass	?
KI 54.44	brass	½ hasta
DM 80.87c-88b	brass	8 añgulas
sole of foot:		
PI 9.89-90	leather	8 añgulas
KI 54.43	leather	1 thumb breadth
MYcomm 4 after x+21	leather	?
DM 80.88c-89b	leather	8 añgulas
chest:		
PI 9.78-79 (belly)	animal	2 ½ hastas
MY 4 x+18	bone of a domestic animal	1 ½ hastas
DM 80.77c-78b	śalya from a domestic animal	2 ½ hastas
heart:		
DM 80.78cd (chest)	heart	heart deep
PI 9.90-91	heart	11 añgulas
MY 4 x+19	heart	½ hasta

flank:		
PI 9.91-92	rib	½ a man
MY 4 x+19	rib	2 hastas
DM 80.79c-80b	sand	flank deep
breast:		
PI 9.92-93	cat rib cage	chest deep
back:		
PI 9.93-94	pig knee	navel deep
MY 4 x+17	pig knee	½ a man / 3 hastas?
DM 80.79ab	something from the back	back deep
eye:		
PI 9.94	pearl	eye deep
MY 4 x+16	pearl	½ a man
ear:		
PI 9.95	coral, gold, silver	ear deep
MY 4 x+16	coral, gold, silver	½ a man
nose:		
MY 4 x+17	perfumed goods	3 hastas?
buttock:		
PI 9.97	tin	hip deep
MYcomm 4 after x+21	tin	½ a man
teeth:		
PI 9.98	mica bowl	3 hastas
MY 4 x+17	talcum	3 hastas
DM 80.70cd	jaw	2 hastas
eye brows:		
PI 9.99	glass	3 hastas
My 4 x+17	glass	3 hastas
armpit:		
PI 9.99	iron	3 hastas
MY 4 x+20	iron	3 hastas
penis:		
PI 9.100	triloha	3 hastas
MY 4 x+21	triloha	1 hasta
entire body:		
PI 9.101	various	all over vāstu

Table 4: Offerings to vāstu deities

<u>deity</u>	<u>offerings</u>	
	KI 54.48-57	MY 4 y+14-y+35
Īśa	ghee, barley	ghee, barley
Parjanya	lotus and water	lotus and water
Jaya	yellow banner	yellow banner
Mahendra	jewels	jewel water
Sūrya	dark canopy	dark canopy
Satya	rice cakes, ghee	wheat gruel, ghee
Bhṛśa	meat	fish
Antarikṣa	bird	groats
Agni	ladle	ladle of meat, milk, ghee
Pūṣan	grain	grain
Vitatha	?	gold water
Gṛhākṣata	honey	honey
Yama	meat, rice	meat, rice
Gandharva	perfume	fragrant powders
Bhṛṅga	bird's tongue	bird's tongue
Mṛga	sesame seeds, barley, sesame	barley sprouts
Pitṛ	sesame seeds, barley, sesame	sesame dish and kedgerree
Dauvārika	tooth-stick	tooth-stick
Sugrīva	barley	cake
Puṣpadanta	kuśa grass	darbha grass
Pracetas	lotus	lotus
Asura	rice beer	rice beer
Śoṣa	food with ghee	food with ghee
Roga	rice gruel	cakes with ghee
Vāyu	rice gruel, ghee	yellow banner
Nāga	various flowers	nāgakeśara flower pollen
Mukhya	cake	masticable food
Bhallāṭa	food with mung beans	mung bean soup
Soma	curd	a vessel of rice pudding and ghee
Ṛgi	lotus root	lotus root
Aditi	lopikā cake	cake
Diti	apūpikā cake	cake
Āpa	milk	curd
Āpavatsa	curd	milk
Savitṛ	kuśa, water	red flowers
Sāvitrī	molasses, rice	kuśa and water
Indra	rice, turmeric	food with turmeric
Indrajaya	rice, turmeric	mixed food
Rudra	flesh	food with ghee
Rudrajaya	flesh	food with meat
Marīci	sweets	sweets
Vivasvat	red sandal	red sandal
Mitra	food with ghee	sweetened rice
Pṛthivīdhara	red beans	beans, meat
Brahmā	sesame, ghee, unhusked barley 5 products of the cow, kuśa	caru oblation, ghee, and 5 products of the cow

Table 4: Offerings to vāstu deities

deity	offerings	
	Piṅgalāmata 9.106-138	Agnipurāṇa 40.2-20
Īśa	ghee	ghee, barley
Parjanya	kṣata grains	lotus and water
Jaya	lotus	banner
Mahendra	banner	jewels
Sūrya	gold water	canopy
Satya	incense and canopy	?
Bhr̥ṣa	wheat oblation, ghee and curd	ghee
Antarikṣa	fish or meat	bird meat
Agni	groats, ghee, honey, curd, with ladle	ladle
Pūṣan	lamps	grain
Vitatha	jewel water	gold
Gṛhākṣata	honey	mixed beverage
Yama	fish, meat	meat, rice
Gandharva	perfume	perfume
Bhr̥ṅga	bird's tongue	bird's tongue
Mṛga	barley plant	dark cloths
Pitṛ	sesame dish, meat	sesame dish
Dauvārika	tooth-stick	tooth-stick
Sugrīva	pūpaka cake	barley
Puṣpadanta	kuśa grass	kuśa grass
Pracetas	lotus	lotus
Asura	rice beer	rice beer
Śoṣa	ghee with food	ghee and water
Roga	rice gruel	cakes
Vāyu	yellow banner	- (missing)
Nāga	nāgakeśara flower	flowers
Mukhya	fruit	masticable foods
Bhallāṭa	soup	mung beans and rice
Soma	food with honey and ghee	honey and milk
Ṛgi	lotus root	lotus root
Aditi	lopikā	lopikā
Diti	pūrikā	purikā
Āpa	milk	milk
Āpavatsa	curd	curd
Savitṛ	flower	red flowers
Sāvitrī	kuśa water	kuśa and rice
Indra	rice and peas	water and turmeric
Indrajaya	food with turmeric	ghee and water
Rudra	food with phalguṣas	cooked meat
Rudrajaya	food with ghee	meat
Marīci	sweets	sweets
Vivasvat	red sandal	red sandal
Mitra	sugar dishes	molasses and milk
Pṛthivīdhara	kumāṣa gruel, meat, fish; + variants	meat, rice and beans
Brahmā	ghee, curd, caru, havya, sesame, unhusked barley, kuśa, 5 products of the cow, caurukī oblation	sesame and rice

Table 5: the consequences of the four sets of āyas in the Bṛhatkālottara and Mayasaṃgraha.

The consequences of the 8 dhvaja āyas

dhvajas	consequences at BK pl 184c-185b	consequences at MY 5.139
dhvaja	sthairyam	sthairyam
dhūma	dāham	ploṣaḥ
siṃha	mahādhairyam	param vīryam
śvan	dainyam	param dainyam
vṛṣabha	dhanasaṃcayaṃ	dhanāni
khara	kleśaḥ	kleśaḥ
gaja	sarvārthasaṃprāptiḥ	saṃpūrṇatā
khaga	vyādhiḥ	vyādhiḥ

The consequences of the 7 svara āyas

svaras	consequences at BK pl 187	consequences at MY 5.138
ṣaḍja	striyaḥ	śuddhiḥ
ṛṣabha	dhanam	dhanam
gāndhāra	saṃṛddhiḥ	paśucayaḥ
madhyama	yatitvam ahitam	pravrajyam
pañcama	viṣa	kāmikā
dhaiyata	daṇḍa	cyutiḥ
niṣāda	mahābhūti	viṣāda

The consequences of the 5 bhūta āyas

bhūtas	consequences at BK pl 185c-186a	consequences at MY 5.137a-c
pṛthivī	dhruvam	sthairyam
jala	āpyāyanam	āpyāyanam
agni	dāha	dīptiḥ
vāyu	uccāṭanam	gamaḥ
vyoma	pañcatā	mādhyastham

The consequences of the 3 agni āyas

agnis	consequences at BK pl 186b-d	consequences at MY 5.137cd
gārhapatya	jñānam	jñānam
āhavaniya	vāsam	vāsaḥ
dakṣiṇa	kṣayam	kṣayaḥ